

Technical reference of the BUOYANT modelling system
(model version 4.20)

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide a comprehensive, detailed description of the technical formulation of the BUOYANT modelling system (Kukkonen et al., 2014). The document includes many of the details that are not available in the scientific journal articles.

Model performance or instructions for running the BUOYANT program are not addressed in this document. Model performance has been addresses, for example, by Nikmo et al. (1999) and Kukkonen et al. (2014). Instructions for installing, compiling and running the program can be found in a separate user's guide (Nikmo et al., 2018).

1.1 Overview of the modelling system

The model is applicable for evaluating the atmospheric dispersion of pollutants originated from strongly buoyant sources. Such sources might be formed, e.g., in accidental warehouse and wild-land fires.

The model can be characterized as being a steady-state, local-scale atmospheric dispersion model. The model is applicable for steady state buoyant plumes within a vertically varying atmosphere, i.e., wind speed, ambient temperature, pressure and density vary with height. An overview of the modelling system has been presented in Fig. 1.

The source is assumed to persist for a sufficient length of time so that the plume achieves a steady state behaviour. The atmosphere surrounding the plume is assumed to be undisturbed by the source, i.e., its characteristics are not affected by the heat released from the source. In the modelling of dispersion, the atmospheric conditions, such as wind velocity and air temperature, are assumed to remain constant both horizontally and temporally. The model should be applied only up to a distance of approximately 100 km from the release location. The terrain is assumed to be sufficiently flat and unobstructed. The concentration predictions are considered to represent the temporal average values of the order of 30-60 minutes.

Fig. 1. A schematic presentation of the dispersion of a fire plume plume, the modelling regimes and the vertical atmospheric structure assumed in the model.

The structure (vertical profiles) of atmosphere assumed by the model is described in Section 2. Source term models for forest and liquid pool fires are presented in Section 3. Behaviour of near- and intermediate-field dispersion of high buoyancy plumes is presented in Section 4. Section 5 describes the evaluation of the subsequent far-field, passive atmospheric dispersion.

1.2 References

- Kukkonen, J., Nikmo, J., Sofiev, M., Riikonen, K., Petäjä, T., Virkkula, A., Levula, J., Schobesberger, S. and Webber, D.M., 2014. Applicability of an integrated plume rise model for the dispersion from wild-land fires. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 7, pp. 2663-2681, doi:10.5194/gmd-7-2663-2014.
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Nikmo, J., Tuovinen, J.-P., Kukkonen, J. and Valkama, I., 1999. A hybrid plume model for local-scale dispersion. *Atmos. Environ.* 33, pp. 4389-4399, doi:10.1016/S1352-2310(99)00223-X.

2 Atmospheric vertical profiles of wind speed, temperature, pressure and density

The vertical structure of the atmosphere is assumed to comprise three distinct layers; atmospheric boundary layer (ABL), capping inversion layer and upper layer (Martin et al., 1997; Kukkonen et al., 2014). The atmospheric structure is shown schematically in Fig. 2. Thickness of the inversion layer can be specified to be 0 m, i.e. describing an atmosphere without an inversion layer. The turning of the wind with height has been ignored.

Fig. 2. A schematic presentation of the vertical atmospheric structure assumed in the model.

2.1 Vertical variation of wind speed

Wind speed in ABL is described with profiles based on the Monin–Obukhov similarity theory (e.g. Garratt, 1994). The wind speed formulations in ABL are presented by Nikmo et al. (2018). In the upper layer, the wind speed is assumed to be constant (representing the geostrophic flow), whereas within the inversion layer the wind speed is assumed to change with constant gradient from its value at the top of the ABL to the geostrophic value (the

constant value within the upper layer). User of the model provides the value of the constant upper layer wind speed.

2.2 Vertical variation of potential temperature

Potential temperature in ABL is described with profiles based on the Monin–Obukhov similarity theory. The potential temperature formulations in ABL are presented by Nikmo et al. (2018). The inversion and upper layers have constant potential temperature gradients. User of the model provides the values of the gradients.

The temperature profile of air (T_a) is determined using the definition of potential temperature (e.g. Seinfeld, 1986)

$$T_a(z) = \theta_a(z) \left(\frac{p(z)}{p_R} \right)^K, \quad (2.2.1)$$

where θ_a is the ambient potential temperature; z is the height above ground; p is the atmospheric pressure; p_R is a reference pressure; and K is the Poisson constant given by

$$K = \frac{R_g}{m_a c_{pa}}, \quad (2.2.2)$$

where R_g is the molar gas constant; m_a is the molecular weight of air; and c_{pa} is the specific heat capacity of air.

2.3 Vertical variations of density and pressure

The density of ambient air, $\rho_a(z)$, is given by the ideal gas law. Substituting for the ambient temperature in terms of the potential temperature, Eq. (2.2.1), into ideal gas law equation yields

$$\rho_a(z) = \frac{m_a}{R_g} \frac{p(z)}{\theta_a(z)} \left(\frac{p_R}{p(z)} \right)^K. \quad (2.3.1)$$

Pressure is obtained by employing the hydrostatic assumption, i.e. the force of gravity is balanced by the vertical component of the atmospheric pressure gradient force

$$\frac{dp(z)}{dz} = -g\rho_a(z), \quad (2.3.2)$$

where g is the acceleration due to gravity. Substituting for the density, Eq. (2.3.1), and integrating yields

$$\left(\frac{p(z)}{p_R}\right)^K = \left(\frac{p(z_{0h})}{p_R}\right)^K - \frac{g}{c_{pa}} \int_{z_{0h}}^z \frac{1}{\theta_a(z)} dz. \quad (2.3.3)$$

where z_{0h} is the roughness length for heat transfer.

2.4 Numerical solution

The integral of Eq. (2.3.3) is approximated with a globally adaptive scheme based on Gauss-Kronrod rules (Piessens et al., 1983). The numerical implementation of the scheme is a Fortran 95 translation of the QUADPACK (2009) procedures.

2.5 References

- Garratt, J.R., 1994. The atmospheric boundary layer. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 316 p.
- Kukkonen, J., Nikmo, J., Sofiev, M., Riikonen, K., Petäjä, T., Virkkula, A., Levula, J., Schobesberger, S. and Webber, D.M., 2014. Applicability of an integrated plume rise model for the dispersion from wild-land fires. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 7, pp. 2663-2681, doi:10.5194/gmd-7-2663-2014.
- Martin, D., Webber, D.M., Jones, S.J., Underwood, B.Y., Tickle, G.A. and Ramsdale, S.A., 1997. Near- and intermediate-field dispersion from strongly buoyant sources, AEA Technology Report AEAT/1388, Warrington, 277 pp.

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QUADPACK, 2009. QUADPACK [online]. [cited 24 Mar 2009]. Available from World Wide Web: <<http://www.netlib.org/quadpack/>>.

Seinfeld, J.H., 1986. Atmospheric chemistry and physics of air pollution. A Wiley Interscience Publication, New York, 738 p.

2.6 Nomenclature

c_{pa}	specific heat capacity (J (kg K)^{-1})
g	acceleration due to gravity (m s^{-2})
K	Poisson constant (-)
m_a	molecular weight (kg kmol^{-1})
p	pressure (Pa)
R_g	molar gas constant (J (kmol K)^{-1})
T_a	temperature (K)
z	height above ground (m)
z_{0h}	roughness length for heat transfer (m)

Greek symbols

θ_a	potential temperature (K)
ρ_a	density (kg m^{-3})

Values of constants

g	= 9.80665 m s^{-1}
R_g	= $8314.472 \text{ J (kmol K)}^{-1}$

3 Evaluation of heat, products and the characteristics of plume generated by a fire

A semi-empirical model is presented for evaluating the initial condition (the “source term”; Fig. 1) for a model of a plume designed for conditions of very high buoyancy (e.g. Kukkonen et al., 2014), such as what might be found, for instance, in toxic plumes of fires.

Spatial or temporal evolution of a fire are not taken into account. The fire is assumed to be circular and horizontal. Further, the fire is assumed to be in the flaming stage. Atmosphere is assumed to be quiescent (calm) with uniform temperature and pressure. The model is limited to forest and liquid pool fires. However, the model structure allows it to be generalized for other types of fires.

3.1 The model in context

The model presented here is designed to estimate the properties of a fire plume just above the flame tips (representing the source term for a plume rise model):

1. The mass fluxes of gaseous and particulate matter produced by a fire.
2. Mass flux of air within a fire plume.
3. The characteristic scales of radius, temperature and vertical velocity of the plume.

In developing the model, the following areas can be identified:

- a) Estimation of mass burning rate (mass of fuel burned in a fire per unit time): Semi-empirical models of mass burning rate are presented for forest and liquid pool fires. Mass fluxes of fire products (e.g. CO, CO₂) are, by definition, determined employing the modelled mass burning rate and experimentally determined yields (or emission factors) of fire products (Sections 3.4, 3.5.1 and 3.5.3).
- b) The total heat flux (rate at which the combustion reactions produce heat/energy) generated by a fire is directly proportional to the mass burning rate. The coefficient of proportionality being the experimentally determined heat of combustion (Section 3.2). The total heat is propagated into the surrounding in the form of convection, radiation

or by other means (e.g. conduction). Models and estimates for evaluating the convective fraction of total heat are presented (Sections 3.4 and 3.5.2).

- c) Convective heat is related to the buoyancy force which arises from the density difference between the fire plume and the surrounding air. Buoyancy force (i.e. convective heat) allows to determine the characteristic scales of a fire plume (Section 3.3.2) in terms of a well-known (but experimentally modified) formulation for a buoyant plume in quiescent atmosphere.
- d) Estimation of mean flame height (Section 3.3.1) at which the characteristic scales of the fire plume are estimated.

3.1.1 Requirements of user input

All of the user input data is assumed to represent constant values in space and time.

Forest fires

- Area of the forest on fire.
- Number of trunks (trees) per unit area of forest on fire.
- Average height of trees on fire.
- Average bole diameter at breast height of trees on fire.

Liquid pool fires

- Name of the fuel (liquid) burning.
- Surface area of the liquid pool on fire.

3.2 Heat generated by fires

The three modes of heat transfer (exchange of thermal energy between physical systems) have been termed conduction, convection and radiation. Radiative transfer does not require a transmitting medium; radiative energy from fires is transmitted by electromagnetic waves. Convective and conductive heat transfer occurs only through a transmitting medium. Heat transfer via mass averaged non-zero velocity (or flux) is termed convection, otherwise

conduction. Convection may be induced naturally (e.g. hot gases rising in atmosphere while air is entrained) or by an external source (e.g. wind). Therefore, convection is usually divided into natural (free) and forced convection. From a conceptual viewpoint, convection is not a basic mode of heat transfer (Atreya, 2016); convection occurs by a combined effect of conduction (and/or radiation) and the motion of the transmitting medium.

The total heat release rate (HRR) of a fire is mostly convected or radiated away from the fire region (Heskestad, 1984 and 2016). Some of the total heat generated by the fire might, for instance, be conducted into the ground beneath the fire (e.g. Ichoku and Kaufman, 2005; Freeborn et al., 2008; Ichoku et al., 2012). The total HRR is often assumed to be equal to the theoretical HRR, which is based on complete combustion of the burning material (Heskestad, 2016). The theoretical HRR (Q) is evaluated as (Heskestad, 2016)

$$Q = q_{m,f}H_c, \tag{3.2.1}$$

where $q_{m,f}$ is the mass burning rate (rate of mass burned of the combusting fuel); and H_c is the lower heat of complete combustion.

The ratio of the total to the theoretical heat release rate (combustion efficiency, χ) is close to unity for some fire sources (e.g. methanol and heptane pools), but may deviate significantly from unity for others (Heskestad, 2016). For instance, $\chi = 0.45$ for a polystyrene fire and $\chi = 0.63$ for a fully involved stack of wood pallets fire has been measured. We have assumed a complete combustion ($\chi = 1$).

The lower, or net, heat of combustion (H_c) refers to the situation in which the fire products are (initially) in the state in which they are formed (e.g. Drysdale, 2016). For instance, any liquid water in the fuel vaporized during the burning process remains in vapour form and does not therefore initially contribute to the heat released by the fire. The higher (or gross) heat of combustion, on the other hand, refers to the situation in which, for instance the latent heat of water vaporization is recovered at or near the flame tips. Therefore, H_c is more relevant and should be used in fire calculations (Flagan and Seinfeld, 1988; Aseeva et al., 2014; Drysdale, 2016).

The heat energy generated by a fire (Q) is propagated in the form of convection (Q_c), radiation (Q_r) and by other (Q_o) means (e.g. conduction)

$$Q = Q_c + Q_r + Q_o \equiv \varepsilon_c Q + \varepsilon_r Q + \varepsilon_o Q, \quad (3.2.2)$$

where ε_c , ε_r and ε_o are the fractions of convective, radiative and other than Q_c and Q_r of the total heat flux Q , respectively (obviously $\varepsilon_c + \varepsilon_r + \varepsilon_o = 1$).

Laboratory experiments on biomass burning have demonstrated values of $\varepsilon_o \sim 0.35$ (Freeborn et al., 2008). Freeborn et al. (2008) conclude that the remainder ($\varepsilon_o Q$) of a biomass burn heat goes to (a) conduction; (b) the energy required to mechanically drive and also evaporate moisture from the fuel; (c) the endothermic energy required to raise the fuel to ignition temperature, and to initiate self-sustaining chemical reactions; and (d) the differences in the heat of combustion between volatiles and char. For large fires ε_r tends to decrease with increasing size of fire (Heskestad, 2016).

Q_c is defined by (e.g. Achtemeier et al., 2012; Kukkonen et al., 2014; Heskestad, 2016)

$$Q_c = c_p \rho u \pi r^2 \Delta T, \quad (3.2.3)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity of the plume (essentially air); ρ is the density of the plume; u is the (characteristic) velocity of the plume; r is the (characteristic) radius of the plume; and $\Delta T = T - T_a$ is the excess temperature of the plume, where T is the (characteristic) temperature of the plume and T_a is the temperature of ambient air.

3.3 Flame height and the fire plume

This section presents methods for evaluating (a) the mean flame height; (b) the characteristic radius, temperature and velocity of a plume above the mean flame height; (c) the elevation of virtual point source from which the plume appears to originate; and (d) the molar content (fluxes of material) of a fire plume. It is assumed that the flames are vertical and the atmosphere is quiescent (calm) with uniform temperature and pressure. The characteristic

scales (radius, temperature, velocity) of the fire plume are evaluated at the mean flame height.

3.3.1 Mean flame height

Mean flame height (or length) is defined in terms of flame intermittency, $I(z)$, which is defined as the fraction of time that at least part of the flame lies above the height z (Heskestad, 2016). $I(z)$ decreases from unity at the fire source to smaller values, eventually reaching zero. The mean flame height is the altitude at which $I(z)$ has declined to 0.5. Mean flame height marks the elevation where the combustion reactions are essentially complete and the inert plume can be considered to begin (Heskestad, 2016).

The mean flame height (L) for a circular fire is approximated with an experimentally determined correlation (Zukoski et al., 1985)

$$L = 3.30dQ^{*2/3}, \quad Q^* < 1, \quad (3.3.1.1)$$

$$L = 3.30dQ^{*2/5}, \quad Q^* \geq 1, \quad (3.3.1.2)$$

where d is the diameter of fire source or equivalent diameter for a noncircular fire in terms of area (i.e. $\pi d^2/4 = \text{area of the fire source}$). The fire Froude number Q^* is defined as

$$Q^* = \frac{Q}{\rho_a c_{pa} T_a (gd)^{1/2} d^2}, \quad (3.3.1.3)$$

where ρ_a is the density of ambient air; c_{pa} is the specific heat capacity of air at constant pressure; and g is the acceleration due to gravity.

A large Froude number ($Q^* \gg 1$) describes a fire for which the energy output is relatively large compared to its physical diameter, like an oil well blowout fire (McGrattan and Miles, 2016). A low value ($Q^* \ll 1$) describes a fire for which the energy output is relatively small compared to its diameter, such as a brush fire.

In the region where $Q^* \geq 1$, the flame height is independent (Eq. (3.3.1.2)) of fire diameter, d , and is proportional to $Q^{2/5}$. For the lower region where $Q^* < 1$ (Eq. (3.3.1.1)), the flame height depends on the diameter, and is proportional to $Q^{2/3}$.

Several other experimentally derived correlations for mean flame height have been proposed. Comparisons of the correlations with experimental data and against each other have been presented by, for instance, Grove and Quintiere (2002), Dupuy et al. (2003), Luketa and Blanchat (2015) and Heskestad (2016).

3.3.2 Radius, temperature, velocity and molar content of a fire plume

The model of Morton-Taylor-Turner (Morton et al., 1956; hereafter referred to as MTT) for low-momentum releases of buoyant material describes a steady plume rising vertically in a calm atmosphere in terms of its characteristic density, radius and upward velocity as a function of vertical coordinate. The MTT model (Appendix A) applies to sources of small differences in density compared to ambient density (Boussinesq approximation), or to a region above the source where air entrainment has brought the plume density sufficiently close to the ambient value. The Boussinesq approximation is used in the field of buoyancy-driven flow where variations in density are neglected, except where they induce buoyancy force (i.e. in terms where density differences appear multiplied by the acceleration due to gravity). Recent studies of the MTT model have presented, for example, Rooney and Linden (1996), Hunt and Kaye (2001), and Fanneløp and Webber (2003).

The solution of the coupled first-order differential equations of the MTT model governing the evolution of the characteristic plume radius, velocity and density deficit ($\Delta\rho = \rho_a - \rho$) above a point source and small density difference can be written in terms of Q_c (e.g. Heskestad, 1998 and 2016)

$$r = \frac{6\alpha}{5} z, \tag{3.3.2.1}$$

$$u = \frac{5}{6} \left(\frac{9}{10\pi\alpha^2} \right)^{1/3} g^{1/3} (c_p \rho_a T_a)^{-1/3} Q_c^{1/3} z^{-1/3}, \tag{3.3.2.2}$$

$$\frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho_a} = \frac{5}{6} \left(\frac{9\pi^2\alpha^4}{10} \right)^{-1/3} g^{-1/3} (c_p\rho_a T_a)^{-2/3} Q_c^{2/3} z^{-5/3}, \quad (3.3.2.3)$$

where α is a dimensionless entrainment coefficient.

The entrainment assumption of the MTT model states that the velocity of entrained air across the plume edge (u_e) is proportional to the plume velocity (often referred to as Morton-Taylor-Turner entrainment model, see Appendix A)

$$u_e = \alpha u. \quad (3.3.2.4)$$

However, there are many instances where plumes are non-Boussinesq. Observations indicate that in the non-Boussinesq case, the entrainment velocity depends on the ratio of the plume density to the ambient value (Ricou and Spalding, 1961). Morton (1965) suggested based on experimental evidence and theoretical considerations an additional proportionality of the entrainment velocity to the square root of the density ratio of the plume and ambient air (usually referred to as Ricou-Spalding entrainment model)

$$u_e = \alpha \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_a} \right)^{1/2} u. \quad (3.3.2.5)$$

Eq. (3.3.2.5) indicates a reduced entrainment into very light turbulent plumes in comparison with plumes of near ambient air density, while entrainment is enhanced into denser-than-air plumes.

Real sources have finite area and in extending the model to other than point sources, a concept of virtual source (or virtual origin) is often introduced. The virtual source is located below the actual area source, and is accounted for in replacing z in Eqs. (3.3.2.1-3) by $z - z_{vs}$, where z_{vs} is the location of the virtual source. Further, to accommodate large density deficiencies, Morton (1965) replaced $\Delta\rho/\rho_a$ in Eq. (3.3.2.3) with $\Delta\rho/\rho$ and added a factor $(\rho_a/\rho)^{1/2}$ on the right-hand side of Eq. (3.3.2.1).

Measurements in fire plumes above the flames have to a large extent supported the theory, with the following results and experimentally adjustable coefficients (Heskestad, 1984 and 1998). The plume radius ($r_{\Delta T}$), and the mean values of velocity (u_0) and excess temperature ($\Delta T_0 = T_0 - T_a$) at the plume centre line have been found to obey the following relations (Heskestad, 1984 and 1998)

$$r_{\Delta T} = C_1 \left(\frac{T_0}{T_a} \right)^{1/2} (z - z_{vs}), \quad (3.3.2.6)$$

$$u_0 = C_2 \left(\frac{g}{c_p \rho_a T_a} \right)^{1/3} Q_c^{1/3} (z - z_{vs})^{-1/3}, \quad (3.3.2.7)$$

$$\Delta T_0 = C_3 \left(\frac{T_a}{g c_p^2 \rho_a^2} \right)^{1/3} Q_c^{2/3} (z - z_{vs})^{-5/3}. \quad (3.3.2.8)$$

where $C_1 = 0.12$, $C_2 = 3.4$ and $C_3 = 9.1$ are experimental coefficients; T_0 is the mean temperature of the plume at centre line; and $r_{\Delta T}$ is the plume radius at the point where the excess temperature is $0.5\Delta T_0$. The above values of coefficients C_i ($i=1,3$) are based on experimental investigations of heated air jets and large-scale pool fires (George Jr. et al., 1977; Kung and Stavrianidis, 1982). For burn experiments in rack storage fires, Kung et al. (1986) (see also Tamanini, 2010) have recommended $C_1 = 0.12$, $C_2 = 4.25$ and $C_3 = 11.0$. We apply the values of C_i presented by Heskestad (1984 and 1998).

For normal atmospheric conditions, and fire sources which do not have substantial in-depth combustion, z_{vs} can be estimated with (Heskestad, 1984)

$$z_{vs} = -1.02d + 0.083 \left(\frac{Q}{1000} \right)^{2/5}. \quad (3.3.2.9)$$

A fire source does not have substantial in-depth combustion if a major fraction of the volatiles released (perhaps 2/3 or greater) undergoes combustion above the fuel array, i.e., if only a minor fraction (perhaps 1/3 or smaller) of the volatiles is oxidized within the fuel array by air entering the array (Heskestad, 1984). Fire sources with substantial in-depth combustion include very openly constructed, or well-ventilated wood cribs.

Eq. (3.3.2.9) has been derived applying experimental data from pool fires varying in diameter from 0.16 to 2.4 m. Heskestad (2016) compared Eq. (3.3.2.9) against three other correlations for z_{vs} . He concluded that “despite the diverse approaches, the overall correlations are surprisingly similar”. Precise measurements are not yet available to clearly identify an optimal correlation for z_{vs} (Heskestad, 2016).

3.3.2.1 Characteristic scales of velocity and temperature of a fire plume

The semi-empirically determined mean velocity and excess temperature (Eqs. (3.3.2.7) and (3.3.2.8)) represent centre line values of a fire plume. Physically, u_0 and ΔT_0 tend to their ambient values as the radial distance from the centre line increases. However, the integral plume rise model described in Section 4 assumes that the plume is described with a uniform (top-hat) distribution of physical quantities. If the centre line values (u_0 , ΔT_0) were to be used as representative of a top hat profile, conservation of convective heat cannot be (usually) achieved (cf. Appendix B). A model to determine characteristic top hat velocity and temperature excess applying their centre line values, while conserving the convective heat is presented in Appendix B. The model assumes Gaussian forms for the radial distributions of velocity and temperature. The profiles may have different widths (scales).

Applying the model and the values of the experimental constants a , C_1 , C_2 and C_3 presented in Appendix B, the characteristic top hat velocity (u) and excess temperature (ΔT) are

$$u = 0.86u_0, \tag{3.3.2.10}$$

$$\Delta T = 0.83\Delta T_0. \tag{3.3.2.11}$$

The model is not applicable for $\pi C_1^2 C_2 C_3 < 1$ (cf. Appendix B).

3.3.2.2 Molar fluxes of a fire plume

Assuming ideal gas behaviour, the molar flux of gaseous material (q_n) of a fire plume is simply

$$q_n = \frac{p_a}{R_g T} \pi r^2 u, \quad (3.3.2.12)$$

where p_a is the atmospheric pressure (pressure within the plume is assumed to be equal to the ambient value); and R_g is the molar gas constant. The flux q_n comprises of the molar fluxes of air ($q_{n,a}$) and gaseous combustion products ($q_{n,c}$)

$$q_n = q_{n,a} + q_{n,c}. \quad (3.3.2.13)$$

3.4 Liquid pool fires

Hottel (1959) was probably the first to suggest how to systematically analyse liquid pool burning data according to basic heat transfer principles (Babrauskas, 1983). According to Hottel (1959) the mass burning rate is governed by the heat exchange between the flame and the pool surface. The heat exchange mechanisms are (a) radiant flux from the flames into the pool; (b) convective flux from the flames into the pool; (c) re-radiant heat loss (Q_{rr}) due to high temperature of the pool; and (d) conduction losses and non-steady terms (Q_{misc}). Quantitative expressions for Q_{misc} are usually not available, while Q_{rr} is often small (Babrauskas, 1983). For simple analysis Q_{rr} and Q_{misc} are customarily ignored (Babrauskas, 1983). Hottel (1959) analyzed the precedent experimental data of Blinov and Khudiakov (1957) concluding that two basic regimes are possible: radiatively dominated burning for large pool diameters and convectively dominated burning for small pools. The distinction between the two regimes can be drawn at pool diameter of approximately 0.2 m (Hottel 1959; Babrauskas, 1983; Chatris et al., 2001). For fire hazard analysis purposes, liquid pool fires will rarely be significantly dangerous if they are smaller than about 0.2 m in diameter (Babrauskas, 2016). Therefore, it will often only be necessary to treat pools burning in the radiative regime.

Zabetakis and Burgess (1961) suggested (see also Babrauskas, 1983; Chatris et al., 2001; Brambilla and Manca, 2009), based on the work of Hottel (1959), the following relationship to represent the mass burning rate ($q_{m,f}$) of a liquid pool in the radiative dominated regime

$$q_{m,f} = q_{m,\infty} A (1 - e^{-k\beta d_p}), \quad (3.4.1)$$

where $q_{m,\infty}$ is the mass burning rate per unit area of an infinite-diameter pool; k is the extinction coefficient of the flame; β is a mean-beam-length corrector; and d_p is the diameter of pool. For small d_p the flames are said to be optically thin, while for larger d_p the flames become optically thick (Babrauskas, 1983) meaning that a further increase in d_p does not result into a corresponding increase in back radiation into the pool. Such attenuation is accounted for by the coefficient $k\beta$ (Brambilla and Manca, 2009).

Values of the empirical coefficients $q_{m,\infty}$ and $k\beta$ for a variety of fuels have been proposed by, for instance, Babrauskas (1983), Rew et al. (1997) and Chatris et al. (2001). User of the model provides the surface area of the burning liquid pool (A) and the name of the liquid fuel burning.

Experimental values of lower heat of complete combustion (H_c) for various burning fuels (liquids) have been tabulated by, for example, Babrauskas (1983), McGrattan et al. (2000) and Hurley (2016).

The total heat generated by a liquid pool fire is assumed to be propagated only through convective and radiative processes, i.e. $\varepsilon_o = 0 \Leftrightarrow \varepsilon_c = 1 - \varepsilon_r$. Radiometer measurements from large fire experiments involving different combustible liquids (crude oil, heptane, kerosene) suggest that the radiative fraction (ε_r) decreases with increasing fire diameter (d) according to (McGrattan et al., 2000)

$$\varepsilon_r = \varepsilon_{max} e^{-kd}, \quad (3.4.2)$$

where $\varepsilon_{max} = 0.35$; and $k = 0.05 \text{ m}^{-1}$.

Yield (y_i) of a fire product i is defined as the ratio of mass generation rate of i to mass burning rate of the combusting fuel (e.g. Tewarson, 1980; Khan et al., 2016)

$$y_i = \frac{m_{w,i} q_{n,i}}{q_{m,f}}, \quad (3.4.3)$$

where $m_{w,i}$ is the molecular weight of species i ; and $q_{n,i}$ is the molar flux of species i . Experimental values of yields under well-ventilated fire conditions have been listed by, for instance, Ross et al. (1996) and Hurley (2016).

Molar fluxes ($q_{n,i}$) of gaseous fire products are calculated using Eq. (3.4.3). Finally, molar flux of air can be calculated utilizing Eqs. (3.3.2.12) and (3.3.2.13).

Examples of fuel property data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Example fuel property data. Notation: H_c , $q_{m,\infty}$ and $k\beta$, see text; y_{CO_2} , y_{CO} , y_{hc} and y_s are the yields of CO₂, CO, hydrocarbons and soot, respectively; dashes = either not measured or are less than 0.001. References: 1 = Babrauskas (1983), 2 = Hurley (2016).

Material	H_c kJ kg ⁻¹	$q_{m,\infty}$ kg (m ² s) ⁻¹	$k\beta$ m ⁻¹	y_{CO_2} g g ⁻¹	y_{CO} g g ⁻¹	y_{hc} g g ⁻¹	y_s g g ⁻¹	References
Acetone (C ₃ H ₆ O)	25800	0.041	1.9	2.14	0.003	0.001	0.014	1,2
Benzene (C ₆ H ₆)	40100	0.085	2.7	2.33	0.067	0.018	0.181	1,2
Butane (C ₄ H ₁₀)	45700	0.078	2.7	2.85	0.007	0.003	0.029	1,2
Heptane (C ₇ H ₁₆)	44600	0.101	1.1	2.85	0.01	0.004	0.037	1,2
Kerosene	43200	0.039	3.5	2.83	0.012	0.004	0.042	1,2
LNG (mostly CH ₄)	50000	0.078	1.1	2.72	–	–	–	1,2
LPG (mostly C ₃ H ₈)	46000	0.099	1.4	2.85	0.005	0.001	0.024	1,2

3.5 Forest fires

3.5.1 Burning rate of woody fuel

The mass burning rate of wild-land fuels is not well understood although numerous studies have been conducted on burning rates of wood cribs (Fig. 3) and match sticks (McAllister et al., 2016a and 2016b). Operational fire models tend to be empirical, predicting the rate of spread of fire while not directly calculating the burning rate (McAllister et al., 2016b). Wood cribs used in fire testing, provide fundamental understanding of the mechanisms governing the burning rate that may be applicable to other fuel beds, such as wild-land fire (McAllister

et al., 2016a). Block (1971) developed the first, and still only, theoretical model of the crib burning rate. Heskestad (1973) combined the experimental results of Gross (1962) and Block (1971) with the theoretical findings of Block (1971) to relate the mass burning rate ($q_{m,f}$) to the porosity (ϕ) of the crib (McAllister and Finney, 2016a)

$$\frac{10^3 q_{m,f}}{A_s b^{-1/2}} = f(\phi), \quad (3.5.1.1)$$

where A_s is the exposed surface area of the sticks in the crib; and b is the thickness of the sticks. The functional form of f is approximately (McAllister and Finney, 2016a)

$$f(\phi) = 1 - e^{-50\phi}. \quad (3.5.1.2)$$

For well-ventilated cribs or loosely-packed porous burning crib, ϕ is large and $f(\phi)$ approaches unity.

Fig. 3. General arrangement of a wood crib (reproduced from Babrauskas, 2016).

Wild-land fuel beds are porous (large ϕ) and three dimensional (McAllister and Finney, 2016a). However, Tang (2017) notes that both well-ventilated and under-ventilated cases exist in forested regions. We have assumed that the fuels beds are porous ($f(\phi) = 1$).

Assuming that the diameter of a tree trunk at breast height (d_{bh}) is a representative value of b , we may approximate the mass burning rate of a wild-land fire (porous fuel bed; $f(\phi) = 1$) by

$$q_{m,f} \approx 10^{-3} A_s d_{bh}^{-1/2}. \quad (3.5.1.3)$$

Further, assuming that all of the trees and each “as a whole” (i.e. from ground to treetop) are on fire, the exposed area can be approximated with

$$A_s = \pi d_{bh} h_t n_t A, \quad (3.5.1.4)$$

where h_t is the average height of the burning trunks (trees); n_t is the number of burning trunks per unit forest area burning; and A is the area of forest on fire. In writing Eq. (3.5.1.4) it is assumed that $\pi d_{bh} h_t$ is a representative value of the outer surface of a tree.

Breast height (d_{bh}) is defined to be 1.3 m above ground (e.g. Feldpausch et al., 2011).

3.5.2 Total heat generated, and its components

Heat generated by a forest fire is estimated with Eqs. (3.2.1) and (3.5.1.3). The lower heat of combustion (H_c) of woody fuel ranges typically from 17.8 to 20.4 MJ kg⁻¹ (e.g. Trentmann et al. 2006; Hurley, 2016). We have therefore applied the middle value of the range ($H_c = 19.1$ MJ kg⁻¹).

The fraction of total energy released by combustion that is available for convection depends on the ambient and fuel conditions and is highly uncertain (Trentmann et al., 2006; Freitas et al., 2010; Kukkonen et al., 2014). Laboratory experiments of biomass burning (Freeborn et al., 2008) have indicated a mean convective fraction of $51.8 \pm 9.0\%$ (determined in terms of higher heat of combustion; i.e. including latent heat released during condensation of water vapour generated by the fire). We have assumed that 55% percent of the total heat generated by a forest fire is available for convection ($\epsilon_c = 0.55$). This is simply in the middle of the commonly accepted range from 0.4 to 0.8 (Trentmann et al., 2002; Freitas et al., 2010).

3.5.3 Yields of combustion products

The emission factor is defined as the amount of the chemical species released per mass of dry biomass burned (Andreae and Merlet, 2001). Therefore, emission factor is equal to the yield of combustion products (y_i), Eq. (3.4.3). Comprehensive data on emission factors for various types of biomass burning have been presented by, for instance, Lemieux et al. (2004), Akagi et al. (2011), Kaiser et al. (2012) and Urbanski (2014). The current model version applies the emission factors which are applicable for land cover class of extratropical forest presented by Kaiser et al. (2012). The extratropical forest class cover fuel types typically found in the northern hemisphere (Kaiser et al., 2012).

3.6 Properties of particulate matter

Particles formed in a forest or a liquid pool fire are assumed to be spherical. Further, they are assumed to be 2.5 μm in diameter having the density of water, i.e. the unit density = 1 kg dm^{-3} .

3.7 References

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3.8 Nomenclature

<i>a</i>	constant (-)
<i>A</i>	area (m ²)
<i>b</i>	thickness (m)
<i>B</i>	buoyancy flux (m ⁴ s ⁻³)
<i>c</i>	dimensionless distance (-)
<i>C</i>	constant (-)
<i>c_p</i>	specific heat capacity (J (kg K) ⁻¹)
<i>d</i>	diameter (m)
<i>D</i>	constant (-)
<i>f</i>	function of porosity (-)
<i>g</i>	acceleration due to gravity (m s ⁻²)
<i>h_t</i>	height of a tree (m)
<i>H_c</i>	lower heat of combustion (J kg ⁻¹)
<i>I</i>	flame intermittency (-)
<i>k</i>	extinction coefficient (m ⁻¹)
<i>L</i>	flame height (m)
<i>m_w</i>	molecular weight (kg kmol ⁻¹)
<i>n_t</i>	number of trees per unit area (m ⁻²)
<i>p_a</i>	pressure (Pa)
<i>q_m</i>	mass flux (kg s ⁻¹)
<i>q_{m,∞}</i>	mass flux per unit area (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
<i>q_n</i>	molar flux (kmol s ⁻¹)
<i>Q</i>	heat release rate (W)
<i>Q*</i>	fire Froude number (-)
<i>r</i>	radius (m)
<i>R</i>	radial distance (m)
<i>R_g</i>	molar gas constant (J (kmol K) ⁻¹)
<i>S_{ΔT}, S_u</i>	scale factors (-)
<i>T</i>	temperature (K)
<i>u</i>	velocity (m s ⁻¹)
<i>u_e</i>	entrainment velocity (m s ⁻¹)
<i>y</i>	yield (g g ⁻¹)
<i>z</i>	height above ground (m)

Greek symbols

α	entrainment coefficient (-)
β	mean-beam-length corrector (-)
χ	combustion efficiency (-)
ε	fraction of heat flux (-)
ϕ	porosity (cm)
ρ	density (kg m ⁻³)
σ	measure of width (m)

Values of constants

g	= 9.80665 m s ⁻¹
R_g	= 8314.472 J (kmol K) ⁻¹

Appendix A. The Morton-Taylor-Turner model

The conservation relations of Morton et al. (1956) model for a point source “weak” plume (Boussinesq approximation), uniform ambient density and zero momentum flux at source may be written as

$$\frac{d}{dz}(r^2u) = 2ru_e, \quad (\text{volume/mass}) \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\frac{d}{dz}(r^2u^2) = r^2g\left(\frac{\rho_a - \rho}{\rho_a}\right), \quad (\text{momentum}) \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\frac{d}{dz}\left(r^2ug\frac{\rho_a - \rho}{\rho_a}\right) = 0, \quad (\text{buoyancy}) \quad (\text{A3})$$

where z is the height above ground; r is the radius the plume; u is the vertical velocity of the plume; u_e is rate of entrained air across the plume edge (entrainment velocity); ρ_a is the density of ambient air; and ρ is the density of the plume. The entrainment velocity is assumed to be proportional to some characteristic velocity at height z (Morton et al., 1956)

$$u_e = \alpha u, \quad (\text{A4})$$

where α is an experimentally defined proportionality constant (known as the entrainment constant) relating the entrainment velocity to the vertical velocity within the plume. The entrainment form of Eq. (A4) is often referred to as Morton-Taylor-Turner entrainment model.

The solution of Eqs. (A1-A3) is (Morton et al., 1956)

$$r = \frac{6\alpha}{5}z, \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$u = \frac{5}{6\alpha}\left(\frac{9}{10}\alpha B\right)^{1/3}z^{-1/3}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$g\frac{\rho_a - \rho}{\rho_a} = \frac{5B}{6\alpha}\left(\frac{9}{10}\alpha B\right)^{-1/3}z^{-5/3}, \quad (\text{A7})$$

where the constant buoyancy flux (force) B is

$$B = r^2 u g \frac{\rho_a - \rho}{\rho_a}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

Assuming ideal gas behaviour, the buoyancy force can be written in terms of convective heat flux (Q_c) as (Heskestad, 2016)

$$B = \frac{g Q_c}{\pi c_p T_a \rho_a}. \quad (\text{A9})$$

Appendix B. Centre line properties of a fire plume and equivalent top-hat profiles

The semi-empirically determined mean velocity (u_0) and excess temperature (ΔT_0) of a fire plume (Eqs. (3.3.2.7) and (3.3.2.8)) representing centre line values are (well) above their ambient values. Physically, they tend to their ambient values as the radial distance from the plume centre line increases. Therefore, the centre line values are usually not representative for a plume rise model assuming the radial variations (of density ρ , velocity u and excess temperature ΔT) from the centre of the plume are uniform out to a well defined radius r (so called “top-hat” distribution). For example, assuming that $r = r_{\Delta T}$ and that the centre line values represent top-hat values, i.e. $\rho = \rho_0$, $u = u_0$ and $\Delta T = \Delta T_0$, yields for the convective heat flux (Eq. (3.2.3), and Eqs. (3.3.2.7) and (3.3.2.8))

$$c_p \rho_0 u_0 \pi r_{\Delta T}^2 \Delta T_0 = \pi C_1^2 C_2 C_3 Q_c \equiv C Q_c, \quad (\text{B1})$$

where ideal gas behaviour, i.e. $T_0/T_a = \rho_a/\rho_0$, has been assumed. For the values of coefficients C_i presented in Eqs. (3.3.2.6-8) $C \approx 1.4$, i.e. approximately 40% convective heat energy would be generated “out of thin air”. A model for determining characteristic scales (top-hat distribution) of a fire plume, while conserving convective heat energy is presented in the following.

Often radial profiles of excess temperature, $\Delta T(r)$, and velocity, $u(r)$, are represented as Gaussian in shape, although there is no theoretical foundation for this distribution (Heskestad, 2016)

$$\Delta T(r) = \Delta T_0 \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r}{\sigma_{\Delta T}}\right)^2\right), \quad (\text{B2})$$

$$u(r) = u_0 \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r}{\sigma_u}\right)^2\right), \quad (\text{B3})$$

where r is the radial distance measured from the centre line of the plume; and $\sigma_{\Delta T}$ and σ_u are the measures of the plume width corresponding to the radial distributions of excess temperature and velocity, respectively. The density of the plume is assumed to have a fixed value across the plume equal to the centre line value (ρ_0).

The radius of the plume, $r_{\Delta T}$, is defined in terms of ΔT_0 (see Section 3.3.2). Similarly, a velocity radius (r_u) can also be defined: r_u is the plume radius to the point where the gas velocity has declined to $0.5u_0$ (Heskestad, 2016). The temperature and velocity profiles may have differing scales, i.e.

$$r_u = ar_{\Delta T}. \quad (\text{B4})$$

Heskestad (2016) notes that the most reliable measurements (George Jr. et al., 1977) indicate that perhaps $a = 1.1$. Other measurements indicate values of a varying from 0.86 through 1.5 (Heskestad, 2016). Heskestad (2016) concludes that the widely differing experimental values of a can be attributed to the difficulty of positioning the measuring probes accurately with respect to the plume centre line and to different, intrinsic errors associated with the diverse types of anemometers used.

Applying Eqs. (B2), (B3) and the definitions of the radiuses $r_{\Delta T}$ and r_u yields

$$\sigma_x = (\ln(2))^{-1/2} r_x \equiv br_x, \quad (\text{B5})$$

where the subscript x is either u or ΔT ; and $b \approx 1.201$.

The top-hat, or characteristic, excess temperature (ΔT) and velocity (u) of the plume can be defined as (integrating Eqs. (B2) and (B3))

$$\Delta T = \Delta T_0 R^{-1} \int_0^R \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r}{br_{\Delta T}}\right)^2\right) dr, \quad (\text{B6})$$

$$u = u_0 R^{-1} \int_0^R \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r}{br_u}\right)^2\right) dr = u_0 R^{-1} \int_0^R \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r}{abr_{\Delta T}}\right)^2\right) dr, \quad (\text{B7})$$

where R is some radial distance from the centre of the plume.

By definition of the error function (*erf*)

$$\int_0^R \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r}{\sigma}\right)^2\right) dr = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \sigma \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{\sigma}\right). \quad (\text{B8})$$

Therefore

$$\Delta T = \Delta T_0 \frac{\sqrt{\pi} b r_{\Delta T}}{2 R} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{b r_{\Delta T}}\right) = \Delta T_0 \frac{\sqrt{\pi} b}{2 c} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{c}{b}\right) \equiv \Delta T_0 s_{\Delta T}, \quad (\text{B9})$$

$$u = u_0 \frac{\sqrt{\pi} a b r_{\Delta T}}{2 R} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{R}{a b r_{\Delta T}}\right) = u_0 \frac{\sqrt{\pi} a b}{2 c} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{c}{a b}\right) \equiv u_0 s_u. \quad (\text{B10})$$

where $c = R/r_{\Delta T}$; and $s_{\Delta T}$ and s_u are dimensionless scale factors.

Substituting ΔT_0 and u_0 in Eq. (B1) with ΔT and u (Eqs. (B9) and (B10)), and requiring conservation of convective heat flux yields

$$s_{\Delta T} s_u = \frac{\pi a b^2}{4 c^2} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{c}{b}\right) \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{c}{a b}\right) = C^{-1}. \quad (\text{B11})$$

Eq. (B11) is an implicit function for c , which can be solved numerically. Let us next examine some properties of the (numerical) problem. From Eq. (B11) we may define a function f

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x^2} \operatorname{erf}(x) \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{a}\right) - \frac{4}{\pi a C} \equiv \frac{1}{x^2} \operatorname{erf}(x) \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{a}\right) - D, \quad (\text{B12})$$

where $x = c b^{-1} > 0$; and $D > 0$ is a constant. The zero point(s) of f straightforwardly determines the radius R , and the scale factors $s_{\Delta T}$ and s_u . Clearly, f is continuous and differentiable. Further (since $0 < \operatorname{erf}(x) \leq 1$, for $x > 0$),

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x^2} \operatorname{erf}(x) \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{a}\right) - D \leq \frac{1}{x^2} - D. \quad (\text{B13})$$

Thus, $f(x) < 0$ for $x > D^{-1/2}$, and any possible zero points of f are within $(0, D^{-1/2}]$. Applying the series expansion (e.g. Abramowitz and Stegun, 1972)

$$efc(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} x \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{3} + \frac{x^4}{10} - \frac{x^6}{42} + \dots \right), \quad (\text{B14})$$

yields

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f(x) = \frac{4}{\pi a} - D = \frac{4}{\pi a} \left(1 - \frac{1}{C} \right). \quad (\text{B15})$$

Hence, for

$$C > 1, \quad (\text{B16})$$

f is positive as $x \rightarrow 0$, and f has at least one zero point. Function f with typical values of experimental coefficients a , C_1 , C_2 and C_3 has been illustrated in Fig. B1.

Fig. B1. Function $f(x)$ (see text; Eq. (B12)), with $a = 1.1$, $C_1 = 0.12$, $C_2 = 3.4$ and $C_3 = 9.1$.

For $C < 1$ conservation of convective heat energy cannot be achieved applying the presented method. Therefore, any possible zero point of f is physically irrelevant. The loss or creation of energy can be deduced as follows. For $C < 1$ the centre line values (u_0 , ΔT_0) “lose” convective heat (cf. Eq. B1). Even less convective heat would be carried along with the

Gaussian profiles integrated over any radius > 0 . Hence, (some) convective heat would be lost over the transition from Gaussian to uniform distribution.

The zero point of $f(x)$ was estimated numerically ($x \in (0, D^{-1/2}]$) with a combination of linear interpolation, inverse quadratic interpolation, and bisection (Brent, 1971). Assuming that $C_1 = 0.12$, $C_2 = 3.4$, $C_3 = 9.1$ and $a = 1.1$, yields

$$c \approx 0.92578, \tag{B17}$$

$$s_{\Delta T} \approx 0.83280, \tag{B18}$$

$$s_u \approx 0.85788. \tag{B19}$$

The value of c (Eq. (B17)) means that the temperature and velocity profiles are integrated almost (93%) up to the point where the temperature excess has been declined to $0.5\Delta T_0$, while the velocity profile is integrated up to 84% of r_u . The top-hat excess temperature (ΔT) and velocity (u) are 83% and 86% of their centre line values, respectively.

Clearly, $s_{\Delta T} = s_u$ for distributions of $\Delta T(r)$ and $u(r)$ with equal scales ($a = 1$). Further, it is obvious that for $a = 1$, $s_{\Delta T} = s_u = (\pi C_1^2 C_2 C_3)^{-1/2}$. For the same coefficients C_i as above, yields $s_{\Delta T} = s_u \approx 0.84525$.

Appendix C. Definition of terms

Porosity is a measure of the air spacing between sticks in a wood crib (McAllister and Finney, 2016a). A densely-packed or closed crib has low porosity (value) while an open or loosely-packed crib has high porosity.

Smoke is a mixture of (1) particulates consisting of soot, semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOC), and solid inorganic compounds; and (2) non-particulates consisting of very volatile organic compounds, volatile organic compounds, and liquid and gaseous inorganic compounds (Newman et al., 2016).

Solid carbonaceous particles present in smoke are defined as **soot** (Khan et al., 2016). Soot generally forms as particles with diameters of the order of several nanometers by a process called as inception or nucleation (Rangwala, 2016).

Wood cribs are taken to mean regular, three dimensional arrays of sticks. Each stick is of a square cross section and of a length much greater than its thickness. The sticks are placed in alternately oriented rows, with an air space separating horizontally adjacent sticks (Babrauskas, 2016).

4 Plume rise and near field dispersion

This section describes a model for a highly buoyant plume within a varying atmosphere. The model was originally developed by Martin et al. (1997). Its further developments and evaluation against two large prescribed wild-land fires have been presented by Kukkonen et al. (2014).

4.1 Assumptions and overall structure of the model

The model is applicable for steady state buoyant plumes within a vertically varying atmosphere, i.e., wind speed, ambient temperature, pressure and density vary with height. The vertical structure of the atmosphere is assumed to comprise three distinct layers (Fig. 2): the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL), capping inversion layer and upper layer. The atmosphere surrounding the plume is assumed to be undisturbed by the source, i.e., its characteristics are not affected by the heat released from the source.

The source is assumed to be circular and horizontal. The gases at the source consist of a mixture of dry air and contaminant gas. Changes in phase (condensation of vapour or evaporation of liquid) are not handled. The plume is allowed to have buoyancy both by virtue of having a higher temperature than its surroundings and because it contains a gas of different molecular weight than that of air. The mixture is assumed to have only vertical velocity at the source. The source is assumed to persist for a sufficient length of time so that the plume achieves a steady state behaviour.

The plume is assumed to remain axially symmetric as it rises (Fig. 4). The radial variation in quantities of interest will be assumed to be described by a “top-hat” profile. The contaminant gas is assumed not to react with the air or change its state from gas. The ordinary differential equations describing the plume will be derived by considering the rate of change of (integral) fluxes along the plume. These equations include those for the fluxes of mass, momentum and heat, closed by an entrainment assumption.

The model also includes a treatment for the plume encountering a temperature inversion above the ABL. Buoyancy is gradually depleted as the plume interacts with the inversion

layer, and the plume may run out of buoyancy while some of the material is still within the mixing layer. Alternatively, the plume may be sufficiently buoyant to fully penetrate the inversion layer.

Fig. 4. A sketch of a buoyant plume (reproduced from Martin et al., 1997). Notation: x = downwind distance, z = height above ground, s = distance along the plume centre line trajectory, R = radius of the plume in the direction normal to the plume axis, θ_s = angle between the direction of the plume and the vertical.

The model equations are framed in terms of a set of integral fluxes (Section 4.2) given as a function of distance s along the plume centre line trajectory. Conservation of bulk quantities (mass, momentum and enthalpy) integrated over the plume cross section is described by the rate of change of fluxes (ordinary differential equations (ODEs); Section 4.3) integrated over the plume cross section. The system of ODEs is closed using an entrainment assumption.

4.2 Integral fluxes

The total mass flux (q ; air and contaminant gas) is given by

$$q = \pi r^2 \rho u, \quad (4.2.1)$$

where r is the radius of the plume; ρ is the mean density of the plume; and u is the mean velocity along the plume centre line.

The constant contaminant flux (S) is given by

$$S = \pi r^2 C u, \quad (4.2.2)$$

where C is the mass concentration of the contaminant.

The momentum fluxes (ϕ_x , ϕ_z) along x (parallel to the ground in the direction of the mean wind) and z (vertical) directions, respectively, are given by

$$\phi_x = q u \sin(\alpha), \quad (4.2.3)$$

$$\phi_z = q u \cos(\alpha), \quad (4.2.4)$$

where α is the angle between the direction of the plume and the vertical.

The excess momentum fluxes (ϕ_x^e , ϕ_z^e) along x and z directions, respectively, are given by

$$\phi_x^e = q (u \sin(\alpha) - u_w(z_s)), \quad (4.2.5)$$

$$\phi_z^e = \phi_z, \quad (4.2.6)$$

where z_s is the height of plume centre line height at the distance, s , along the plume centre line trajectory; and $u_w(z_s)$ is the mean wind speed at z_s .

The excess enthalpy flux (H^e) is given by

$$H^e = (\theta - \theta_a(z_s)) c_{pa} (q + k), \quad (4.2.7)$$

where θ is the potential temperature of the plume; θ_a is the potential temperature of ambient air; c_{pa} is the specific heat capacity of air; and for convenience,

$$k = \left(\frac{c_{pg}}{c_{pa}} - 1 \right) S, \quad (4.2.8)$$

where c_{pg} is the specific heat capacity of the contaminant gas. It should be noted that, since S is assumed to be constant and ignoring any (small) variation in the specific heat capacities with temperature, k is constant.

4.3 Conservation equations

The total mass flux changes due to entrainment of air. The rate of change of mass flux is

$$\frac{dq}{ds} = 2\pi r \rho_a(z_s) u_e, \quad (4.3.1)$$

where ρ_a is the density of ambient air; and the entrainment velocity (u_e) is given by

$$u_e = \alpha_1 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_a(z_s)} \right)^{1/2} |u - u_w(z_s) \sin(\alpha)| + \alpha_2 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_a(z_s)} \right)^{1/2} u_w(z_s) |\cos(\alpha)|, \quad (4.3.2)$$

where α_1 and α_2 are the along and cross-plume air entrainment coefficients, respectively. The form of the entrainment terms is after Ricou and Spalding (1961). For detailed discussion of the form of u_e and modifications compared to the original formulation presented by Martin et al. (1997) the reader is referred to Kukkonen et al. (2014).

As the concentration flux is conserved, the following can be obtained

$$\frac{dS}{ds} = 0. \quad (4.3.3)$$

The rate of change of momentum fluxes are

$$\frac{d\phi_x}{ds} = F^{(m)} = \frac{dq}{ds} u_w(z_s), \quad (4.3.4)$$

$$\frac{d\phi_z}{ds} = F^{(b)} = \frac{\pi r^2 g(\rho_a(z_s) - \rho)}{1 + k_v \sin(\alpha)}, \quad (4.3.5)$$

where $F^{(m)}$ is a term for the entrainment of momentum due to the air; $F^{(b)}$ is the buoyancy force; g is the acceleration due to gravity; and k_v is a coefficient for the added mass term (of order 1). The denominator of the vertical momentum flux equation is a term for added mass included to account for the plume having to push air out of the way as it rises; this term has been written by analogy to the behaviour of a line thermal (Martin et al., 1997).

The change in horizontal and vertical excess momentum fluxes are

$$\frac{d\phi_x^e}{ds} = -\frac{\overline{du_w}}{dz} q \cos(\alpha), \quad (4.3.6)$$

$$\frac{d\phi_z^e}{ds} = \frac{d\phi_z}{ds}, \quad (4.3.7)$$

where $\overline{du_w}/dz$ is the mean representative wind speed gradient. The plume equations are derived on the assumption that the gradients in ambient atmospheric properties are constant across the plume cross section.

In considering the behaviour of a rising plume contacting an elevated inversion, the mean representative wind speed gradient is an area-weighted average defined as

$$\frac{\overline{du_w}}{dz} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{du_w}{dz} \right)_i f_i, \quad (4.3.8)$$

where $i = 1, 2, 3$ correspond to the ABL, inversion layer and upper layer, respectively; $(du_w/dz)_i$ is a representative value for the portion of plume within the i th layer; and f_i is the fraction of plume cross-sectional area lying in the i th layer. In each layer, du_w/dz is taken at the middle-point of the plume vertical extent within the layer. The fractions f_i are

$$f_1 = f(z_s, z_A), \quad (4.3.9)$$

$$f_2 = f(z_s, z_B) - f(z_s, z_A), \quad (4.3.10)$$

$$f_3 = 1 - f(z_s, z_B), \quad (4.3.11)$$

where clearly $\sum f_i = 1$; z_A is the height of the ABL; z_B is the height of upper bound of the inversion layer; and

$$f(z_s, z) = \frac{\cos^{-1}(\eta) - \eta(1 - \eta^2)^{1/2}}{\pi}, \quad (4.3.12)$$

where

$$\eta = \frac{z_s - z}{r \sin(\alpha)}. \quad (4.3.13)$$

If $\eta < 0$ the angle from \cos^{-1} in Eq. (4.3.12) is interpreted to belong to the second quadrant.

The rate of change of the excess enthalpy flux is given by

$$\frac{dH^e}{ds} = -\frac{d\bar{\theta}_a}{dz} \cos(\alpha) c_{pa}(q + k), \quad (4.3.14)$$

where the mean representative gradient of θ_a is defined analogously to the mean wind speed gradient, Eq. (4.3.8), i.e.

$$\frac{d\bar{\theta}_a}{dz} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{d\theta_a}{dz} \right)_i f_i. \quad (4.3.15)$$

The trajectory of the plume is obtained from the following simple kinematic relationships

$$\frac{dx}{ds} = \sin(\alpha), \quad (4.3.16)$$

$$\frac{dz}{ds} = \cos(\alpha), \quad (4.3.17)$$

where x is the downwind distance from the source.

4.4 Quantities describing the plume

The quantities, which describe the plume can be determined from the fluxes. The plume temperature (T), mean velocity along the plume, angle to the vertical, cross-sectional area of the plume (a), and altitudes of upper (z_u) and lower (z_l) edges of the plume are given by

$$T = \theta \left(\frac{p_a(z_s)}{p_R} \right)^K, \quad (4.4.1)$$

$$u = \frac{((\phi_x^e)^2 + (\phi_z^e)^2)^{1/2}}{q}, \quad (4.4.2)$$

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\phi_x}{\phi_z^e} \right), \quad (4.4.3)$$

$$a = \frac{(q + S(m_a m_g^{-1} - 1)) \theta}{u \rho_a(z_s) \theta_a(z_s)}, \quad (4.4.4)$$

$$z_u = z_s + r |\sin(\alpha)|, \quad (4.4.5)$$

$$z_l = z_s - r |\sin(\alpha)|, \quad (4.4.6)$$

where p_R is a reference pressure; p_a is the air pressure; m_a and m_g are the molecular weights of air and contaminant, respectively; and the Poisson constant (K) is

$$K = \frac{R_g}{m_a c_{pa}}, \quad (4.4.7)$$

where R_g is the molar gas constant.

4.5 Criteria for the termination of plume rise

The plume rise is considered to be terminated at the height where the buoyancy force, $F^{(b)}$, first becomes zero. For a detailed discussion on the termination criterion see Kukkonen et al. (2014).

4.6 Numerical solution

The set of coupled ordinary differential equations that consists of Eqs. (4.3.1), (4.3.4), (4.3.6), (4.3.7), (4.3.14), (4.3.16) and (4.3.17) does not have an analytical solution. The set of equations is therefore solved numerically, applying a variable order (one through five) backward differentiation formulae (BDF; Gear, 1971). The BDF method is primarily designed to solve stiff differential equations. The numerical code (DDRIV3/SDRIV3) is implemented by Kahaner and Sutherland (1979) and is part of the public domain SLATEC (1993) procedures.

The DDRIV3/SDRIV3 –procedures allow for obtaining output at points which are not known in advance, but depend upon the solution, for instance, when some solution component takes on a specified value. This option is employed to determine the termination of the plume rise (for the criteria see Section 4.5).

4.7 References

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4.8 Nomenclature

a	area (m ²)
c_p	specific heat capacity (J (kg K) ⁻¹)
C	concentration (kg m ⁻³)
f	fraction (-)
$F^{(b)}$	buoyancy force (kg s ⁻²)
$F^{(m)}$	entrainment of momentum (kg s ⁻²)
g	acceleration due to gravity (m s ⁻²)
H^e	excess enthalpy flux (J s ⁻¹)
k	constant (kg s ⁻¹)
K	Poisson constant (-)
k_v	coefficient for added mass term (-)
m_a, m_g	molecular weight (kg kmol ⁻¹)
p	pressure (Pa)
q	mass flux (kg s ⁻¹)
r	radius (m)
R	radius (m)
R_g	molar gas constant (J (kmol K) ⁻¹)
s	distance (m)
S	contaminant flux (kg s ⁻¹)
T	temperature (K)
u	velocity (m s ⁻¹)
u_e	entrainment velocity (m s ⁻¹)
x	downwind distance (m)
z	height above ground (m)

Greek symbols

α	angle (radians)
α_1, α_2	along and cross-plume entrainment coefficients (-)
ϕ	momentum flux (kg m s ⁻²)
η	auxiliary variable (-)
θ	potential temperature (K)
θ_s	angle (radians)
ρ	density (kg m ⁻³)

Values of constants

α_1	= 0.08
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$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2 &= 0.7 \\ g &= 9.80665 \text{ m s}^{-1} \\ k_v &= 1 \\ R_g &= 8314.472 \text{ J (kmol K)}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

5 Far-field dispersion

Far-field atmospheric dispersion following the plume rise regime (Section 4) is described with a local-scale dispersion model based on atmospheric boundary layer scaling theory. In the vicinity of the source (end of the plume rise regime), Gaussian equations are used in both the horizontal and vertical directions. After a specified transition distance, gradient transfer theory (K-model) is applied in the vertical direction, while the horizontal dispersion is still assumed to be Gaussian. Alternatively, the transition to K-model in the vertical direction can be forced to take place immediately at the end of the plume rise regime.

The original hybrid plume model for local-scale atmospheric dispersion has been described by Nikmo et al. (1997 and 1999). This section presents further developments of the model, corrections made, and details of the numerical solution of the model equations.

5.1 Atmospheric profiles of wind and eddy diffusivity

Stability (ϕ_m, ϕ_h) and influence (ψ_m, ψ_h) functions for momentum and heat transfer have been replaced by those presented by in Section 2.

5.2 Gaussian virtual point source at transition from plume rise to far-field dispersion

The formulation for a Gaussian concentration distribution presented by Nikmo et al. (1997) (their Eq. (42)) is in error. However, for ground level releases it correctly describes vertically unlimited, upwards diffusion with total reflection at ground. Neglecting deposition processes, assuming chemically inert pollutant, unlimited vertically upwards diffusion and total reflection at the ground (non-absorbing ground), the atmospheric dispersion of pollutants emitted from a point source is (correctly) described with

$$C = \frac{q}{u_m} F_y F_z, \quad (5.2.1)$$

where C is the concentration; q is the emission rate; u_m is the mean horizontal plume transport speed within the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL); and the lateral crosswind (F_y) and vertical (F_z) diffusion terms are given by

$$F_y = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{1/2}\sigma_y} \exp\left(\frac{-y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right), \quad (5.2.2)$$

$$F_z = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{1/2}\sigma_z} \left[\exp\left(\frac{-(z-z_e)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right) + \exp\left(\frac{-(z+z_e)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right) \right], \quad (5.2.3)$$

where σ_y and σ_z are the crosswind and vertical dispersion parameters, respectively; y is the lateral distance measured perpendicular to the centre line of the plume; z is the height above ground; and z_e is the altitude of emission above ground. z_e is assumed to be equal to the elevation of the plume centre at final rise height evaluated with the plume rise model described in Section 4.

5.2.1 Mean transport speed

The mean horizontal plume transport speed within ABL is defined to be (Nikmo et al., 1997; their Eq. (39))

$$u_m = \frac{\int_{z_0}^h u(z)C^y(x,z)dz}{\int_{z_0}^h C^y(x,z)dz}. \quad (5.2.1.1)$$

where z_0 is the roughness length of momentum transfer; h is the height of ABL; u is the wind speed; x is the downwind distance and $C^y(x,z)$ is the crosswind integrated concentration. Note that the upper limit of the integrals of Eq. (5.2.1.1) is h instead of infinity as in Nikmo et al. (1997) (their Eq. (39)). For the concentration profiles given by Eq. (5.2.1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 C^y(x, z) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} C(x, y, z) dy \\
 &= \frac{q}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_z u_m} \left[\exp\left(\frac{-(z - z_e)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right) + \exp\left(\frac{-(z + z_e)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right) \right] \\
 &\equiv \frac{q}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_z u_m} f(z).
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.2.1.2}$$

Thus, relation (5.2.1.1) yields

$$u_m = \frac{\int_{z_0}^h u(z) f(z) dz}{\int_{z_0}^h f(z) dz}. \tag{5.2.1.3}$$

The divisor of Eq. (5.2.1.3) can be solved to give

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{z_0}^h f(z) dz &= \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sigma_z \left[\operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{z_0 - z_e}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_z}\right) - \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{h - z_e}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_z}\right) + \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{z_0 + z_e}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_z}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{h + z_e}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_z}\right) \right],
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.2.1.4}$$

where *erfc* is the complementary error function.

5.2.2 Dispersion parameters and the location of virtual source

The lateral and vertical dispersion parameters at the final plume rise are determined using the procedure presented by Kukkonen et al. (2014) (their Appendix A)

$$\sigma_y^2 = \sigma_z^2 = 0.5r^2 [\ln(10)]^{-1}, \tag{5.2.2.1}$$

where *r* is the top-hat radius of the plume at final plume rise.

Previous model codes applied a numerical algorithm to determine the location (travel time) of a virtual source. However, the equation can be solved to give a more precise and less error

prone analytical form. The lateral dispersion parameter is of the form (Nikmo et al., 1997; their Eq. (43))

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_v \frac{t}{1 + [t(2T_{Ly})^{-1}]^{1/2}}, \quad (5.2.2.2)$$

where σ_v is the standard deviation of lateral wind fluctuation; t is the travel time; and T_{Ly} is the Lagrangian time scale for crosswind dispersion. Change of variable, $\tau = t^{1/2} \geq 0$, yields a quadratic equation for τ

$$\tau^2 - (2T_{Ly})^{-1/2} \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_v} \tau - \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_v} = 0. \quad (5.2.2.3)$$

Eq. (5.2.2.3) has two distinct real valued roots (for $\sigma_y > 0$; $\sigma_v > 0$) of which the other is negative and is therefore rejected. The positive root is

$$\tau = t^{1/2} = (8T_{Ly})^{-1/2} \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_v} + \left[(8T_{Ly})^{-1} \left(\frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_v} \right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_v} \right]^{1/2}. \quad (5.2.2.3)$$

The emission height, z_e , may locate above the ABL where the applied formulation of σ_v (Nikmo et al., 1997) is not applicable, it is therefore evaluated at the height z_σ

$$z_\sigma = \min(z_e, 0.95h). \quad (5.2.2.4)$$

5.3 Gaussian rectangular source at transition from plume rise to far-field dispersion

5.3.1 Spatial scales and elevation of the source

The top-hat area (a) within ABL of the plume at final plume rise is

$$a = f\pi r^2, \quad (5.3.1.1)$$

where f is the fraction of the plume cross-sectional area lying in ABL; and r is the top-hat radius of the plume at final plume rise. Assuming the source is an equivalent square in terms of area perpendicular to the mean wind direction, the height (h_s) and width (w_s) of the source are

$$h_s = w_s = a^{1/2}. \quad (5.3.1.2)$$

The middle point of the source is positioned at the centre of the plume at final rise. However, all of the source area has to be within ABL. Thus, the height above ground of the upper edge of the source area (z_{ue}) is set (adjusted) to

$$z_{ue} = \min(h, z_{pr} + h_s/2). \quad (5.3.1.3)$$

5.3.2 Crosswind integrated concentration

Integrating the concentration distribution in crosswind direction for a Gaussian rectangular area source involves the calculation of the integral (notation follows that of Nikmo et al., 1997, their Eq. (40))

$$K = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{y - y_1}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_y} \right) - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{y - y_2}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_y} \right) \right] dy. \quad (5.3.2.1)$$

Suitably selecting the coordinate system, we may define a half width of the source area, $w > 0$, so that $-y_1 = y_2 = w$. Further, for shorter notation we define $b \equiv \sqrt{2}\sigma_y$. Thus

$$K = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{y + w}{b} \right) - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{y - w}{b} \right) \right] dy \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y) dy = 2 \int_0^{\infty} f(y) dy, \quad (5.3.2.2)$$

where the symmetry relation of erf is applied (i.e. it is straightforward to verify that $f(-y) = f(y)$). Substituting $\operatorname{erf}(x) = 1 - \operatorname{erfc}(x)$ and $x = (y \pm w)b^{-1} \Rightarrow dy = bdx$, yields

$$K = 2b \left[\int_{-w/b}^{\infty} \text{erfc}(x) dx - \int_{w/b}^{\infty} \text{erfc}(x) dx \right]. \quad (5.3.2.3)$$

Since (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1972;, their Eqs. (7.2.1), (7.2.3) and (7.2.5))

$$\int_x^{\infty} \text{erfc}(t) dt = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-x^2} - x \text{erfc}(x), \quad (5.3.2.4)$$

yields (note: $\text{erfc}(x) + \text{erfc}(-x) = 2$)

$$K = 2b \frac{w}{b} \left[\text{erfc}\left(-\frac{w}{b}\right) + \text{erfc}\left(\frac{w}{b}\right) \right] = 4w. \quad (5.3.2.5)$$

5.3.3 Transition from Gaussian rectangular source model to K model

Transition from Gaussian to K model is determined by a slightly modified criterion compared to Nikmo et al. (1997, their Eq. (58))

$$2.14\sigma_z = 5l_e, \quad (5.3.3.1)$$

where l_e is the length scale for turbulent transport. Previous code versions solved the Eq. (5.3.3.1) with a numerical algorithm. However, Eq. (5.3.3.1) is the same form as Eq. (5.2.2.1); thus an analytical solution exists. The transport time (t) to the transition point is

$$t = \left\{ (8T_{Lz})^{-1/2} c + [(8T_{Lz})^{-1} c^2 + c]^{1/2} \right\}^2, \quad (5.3.3.2)$$

where T_{Lz} is the Langrangian time scale for vertical dispersion; and the constant c is

$$c = \frac{5l_e}{2.14\sigma_w}, \quad (5.3.3.3)$$

where σ_w is the standard deviation of vertical wind speed fluctuation.

5.4 Numerical solution

Atmospheric diffusion equation

For solving the atmospheric diffusion equation (Nikmo et al., 1999, their Eq. (7)) we have adopted a six-point finite difference scheme. In the horizontal direction an implicit differencing method is used, in which the values at two succeeding distances are weighted equally (Crank-Nicholson method). In the vertical direction discretization is performed with respect to the flux density by employing a staggered grid, in which the flux approximations are realized mid-way the actual grid points. A detailed description of the numerical method is given in Appendix A.

Mean transport speed

The dividend of Eq. (5.2.1.1), i.e. the integral $\int_{z_0}^h u(z)f(z)dz$, is approximated with a globally adaptive scheme based on Gauss-Kronrod rules (Piessens et al., 1983). The numerical implementation of the scheme is a Fortran 95 translation of the QUADPACK (2009) procedures.

Deposition of particles

Terminal settling velocity (v_{ts}) in Newton's drag region (where Reynolds number, Re , is greater than one) is an implicit equation for v_{ts} , or equivalently for Re . For particle motion with $Re > 1$ the terminal velocity can be written as (Hinds, 1982)

$$C_D Re^2 = \frac{4}{3} \frac{d^3 \rho_p \rho_a g}{\mu_a^2}, \quad (5.4.1)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient which depends on Re ; d is the diameter of particle; ρ_p is the density of particle; ρ_a is the density of ambient air; g is the acceleration due to gravity; and μ_a is the dynamic viscosity of air. From Eq. (5.4.1) we may define a function f

$$f(Re) = C_D Re^2 - \frac{4}{3} \frac{d^3 \rho_p \rho_a g}{\mu_a^2}. \quad (5.4.2)$$

Clearly, the zero point of $f(Re)$ is the value of Re at v_{ts} . The zero point of $f(Re)$ is estimated numerically with a combination of linear interpolation, inverse quadratic interpolation, and bisection (Brent, 1971). The zero point is searched between $1 \leq Re \leq 2 \times 10^5$.

5.5 References

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5.6 Nomenclature

a	area (m^2)
b	constant (m)
C	concentration (kg m^{-3})
C_D	drag coefficient (-)
C_V	crosswind integrated concentration (kg m^{-2})
d	diameter (m)
f	fraction; function (-)
F	mass flux ($\text{kg (m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$)
F_y, F_z	diffusion term (m^{-1})
g	acceleration due to gravity (m s^{-2})
h	height (m)
K	constant (m)
K_z	eddy diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
l_e	length scale (m)
q	mass flux (kg s^{-1})
r	radius (m)
Re	Reynolds number (-)
t	time (s)
T_L	Lagrangian time scale (s)
u	velocity (m s^{-1})
v_d	dry deposition velocity (m s^{-1})
v_e	deposition (m s^{-1})
v_{ts}	terminal settling velocity (m s^{-1})
w	width (m)
x	downwind distance (m)
y	crosswind distance (m)
z	height above ground (m)
z_0	roughness length (m)

Greek symbols

ϕ	stability function (-)
λ	constant (-)
μ	dynamic viscosity (kg (m s)^{-1})
ρ	density (kg m^{-3})
σ_v, σ_w	standard deviation of wind fluctuation (m)
σ_y, σ_z	dispersion parameter (m)
τ	auxiliar variable ($\text{s}^{1/2}$)
ψ	influence function (-)

Appendix A. Numerical solution of the atmospheric diffusion equation

The cross-wind integrated steady-state atmospheric diffusion equation without chemical reactions, sinks or sources can be written as

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} K_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \equiv \frac{\partial F}{\partial z}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where u is the wind speed; C is the cross-wind integrated concentration; x and z are the downwind and vertical coordinates; K_z is the vertical eddy diffusivity; and F is the vertical mass flux. In the vertical direction, the boundary conditions are defined as

$$K_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = v_d C, \quad z = z_s, \quad (\text{A2a})$$

$$K_z \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = -v_e C, \quad z = h, \quad (\text{A2b})$$

where v_d is the dry deposition velocity; v_e is the corresponding velocity for the flux through the top of the mixing layer; z_s is a reference height just above the ground; and h is the height of the mixing layer.

Eq. (A1) is discretized in downwind direction between $[0, x_{max}]$ at points $\{x_n\}$, $n=0,1,\dots,N$ and in the vertical direction between $[z_s, h]$ at points $\{z_i\}$, $i=1,2,\dots,P$. Differences in downwind direction are

$$\Delta x = x_{n+1} - x_n, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Grid intervals in the vertical are defined as

$$\Delta z_i = z_{i+1} - z_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P - 1. \quad (\text{A4})$$

With the help of auxiliary vertical grid points $z_0 = z_1$ and $z_{(P+1)} = z_P$ we define the middle points (z_i^m) of the vertical grid and their intervals (Δz_i^m)

$$z_i^m = (z_i + z_{i+1})/2, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P - 1, \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$\Delta z_i^m = z_i^m - z_{i-1}^m, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P. \quad (\text{A6})$$

The flux Eq. (A1) can be discretized with a difference method applying the general form presented for the time dependent, one-dimensional heat conduction equation (Tuovinen, 1992; Richtmyer and Morton, 1967)

$$u_i \frac{C_i^{n+1} - C_i^n}{\Delta x} = \lambda \frac{F_i^{n+1} - F_{i-1}^{n+1}}{\Delta z_i} + (1 - \lambda) \frac{F_i^n - F_{i-1}^n}{\Delta z_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P, \quad (\text{A7})$$

where the fluxes are given at the grid middle points $F_i^n = F^n(z_i^m)$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ is the weight factor of x -steps (time steps in the heat conduction equation). When $\lambda = 0$, the equation is a explicit four point method wherein the differences in x -direction are formed forward. For $\lambda \neq 0$, the method is implicit. If $\lambda = 1/2$ (Crank-Nicholson method), six grid points is used and the differences in x -direction are central differences. With four point implicit method ($\lambda = 1$) differences in x -direction are formed backwards (Laasonen method). Here we apply the Crank-Nicholson method ($\lambda = 1/2$), thus the successive points in x -direction are equally weighted.

The vertical mass flux is approximated around the middle points of the vertical grid

$$F_i^n = K_i^m \frac{C_{i+1}^n - C_i^n}{\Delta z_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P - 1, \quad (\text{A8})$$

where the eddy diffusivities are given at the middle points $K_i^m = K_z(z_i^m)$. Thus, the vertical grid is overlapped so that the wind speed and concentration are given at the actual grid points while the vertical mass flux is taken at the middle points.

The mass fluxes at the top and bottom boundaries follows from Eqs. (A2a-b)

$$F_0^n = v_d C_1^n, \quad (\text{A9a})$$

$$F_P^n = -v_e C_P^n. \quad (\text{A9b})$$

Substituting the mass fluxes into Eq. (A7) yields a linear algebraic set of equations

$$e_1 C_2^{n+1} + q_1 C_1^{n+1} = r_1, \quad (\text{A10a})$$

$$e_i C_{i+1}^{n+1} + q_i C_i^{n+1} + d_i C_{i-1}^{n+1} = r_i, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, P-1, \quad (\text{A10b})$$

$$q_P C_P^{n+1} + d_P C_{P-1}^{n+1} = r_P. \quad (\text{A10c})$$

The task is to invert a matrix having non-zero elements only on three main diagonals. The elements of the matrix are

$$e_i = \frac{-\lambda K_i^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_i \Delta z_i^m u_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P-1, \quad (\text{A11})$$

$$d_i = \frac{-\lambda K_{i-1}^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_{i-1} \Delta z_i^m u_i}, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, P, \quad (\text{A12})$$

$$q_1 = 1 - e_1 + \frac{\lambda v_d \Delta x}{\Delta z_1^m u_1}, \quad (\text{A13a})$$

$$q_i = 1 - e_i - d_i, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, P-1, \quad (\text{A13b})$$

$$q_P = 1 - d_P + \frac{\lambda v_e \Delta x}{\Delta z_P^m u_P}, \quad (\text{A13c})$$

$$r_1 = \frac{(1-\lambda)K_1^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_1 \Delta z_1^m u_1} C_2^n + \left(1 - \frac{(1-\lambda)K_1^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_1 \Delta z_1^m u_1} - \frac{(1-\lambda)v_d \Delta x}{\Delta z_1^m u_1}\right) C_1^n, \quad (\text{A14a})$$

$$r_i = \frac{(1-\lambda)K_i^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_i \Delta z_i^m u_i} C_{i+1}^n + \left(1 - \frac{(1-\lambda)K_i^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_i \Delta z_i^m u_i} - \frac{(1-\lambda)K_{i-1}^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_{i-1} \Delta z_i^m u_i}\right) C_i^n + \frac{(1-\lambda)K_{i-1}^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_{i-1} \Delta z_i^m u_i} C_{i-1}^n, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, P-1, \quad (\text{A14b})$$

$$r_P = \left(1 - \frac{(1-\lambda)K_{P-1}^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_{P-1} \Delta z_P^m u_P} - \frac{(1-\lambda)v_e \Delta x}{\Delta z_P^m u_P}\right) C_P^n + \frac{(1-\lambda)K_{P-1}^m \Delta x}{\Delta z_{P-1} \Delta z_P^m u_P} C_{P-1}^n. \quad (\text{A14c})$$

The solution of the algebraic set of Eqs. (A10a-c) can be written in the form

$$C_P = b_P, \quad (\text{A15a})$$

$$C_i = a_i C_{i+1} + b_i, \quad i = P-1, P-2, \dots, 1. \quad (\text{A15b})$$

The coefficients a_i and b_i are solved by substituting the Eqs. (A15a-b) into the Eqs. (A10a-c)

$$a_1 = \frac{-e_1}{q_1}, \quad (A16a)$$

$$a_i = \frac{-e_i}{q_i + d_i a_{i-1}}, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, P-1, \quad (A16b)$$

$$b_1 = \frac{r_1}{q_1}, \quad (A17a)$$

$$b_i = \frac{r_i - d_i b_{i-1}}{q_i + d_i a_{i-1}}, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, P. \quad (A17b)$$

In order to avoid accumulation of rounding errors, it is required that $a_i \leq 1$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, P-1$. This requirement is easily reduced to condition $a_1 \leq 1$, as $-e_i \leq q_i + d_i$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, P-1$. Since

$$a_1 = -e_1 \left(1 - e_1 + \frac{\lambda v_d \Delta x}{\Delta z_1^m u_1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (A18)$$

yields a condition $\lambda v_d \Delta x (\Delta z_1^m u_1)^{-1} \geq -1$, which is always valid.

The method is a modification of the Gaussian elimination method. It requires noticeably less work than a direct solution with inverse matrix, where after calculating the inverse matrix we need to calculate at every x -step the product of a matrix and a vector for each vertical grid point.

Vertical and downwind grids

We have selected a linear vertical grid having a spacing (Δz) of approximately one metre

$$\Delta z = \frac{h - z_1}{\text{int}(h - z_1)}, \quad (A19)$$

where $z_1 = 1.1 z_0$ is the lowest grid level; z_0 is the roughness length for momentum transfer; and $\text{int}(x)$ is a function whose value is the argument (x) truncated towards zero to the nearest whole integer number.

A variable spacing is also used in the downwind direction (Nikmo et al., 1997), with the grid points in metres varying as $\{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots\} = \{0.001, 0.002, \dots, 0.009, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.09, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 0.9, 1, 2, \dots, 9, 10, 20, \dots, 90, 100, 200, 300, \dots\}$, with maximum grid interval of 100 m.